

Nucula (Nuculidae, Bivalvia) from upper bathyal depths off Namibia

Nucula (Nuculidae, Bivalvia) del piso batial superior frente a Namibia

Michael L. ZETTLER* & Leon HOFFMAN**

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ABSTRACT

Three species were found from the continental slope off Namibia of which two species are new to science: *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp. and *N. nama* n. sp. A comparison was made with morphologically similar eastern Atlantic and South African species in the family Nuculidae. *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp. was found alive in silty sediment with high organic content in upper bathyal depths off the Kunene region in NW Namibia. *Nucula nama* n. sp. is only known from a single living individual taken in a similar environment. The two new species have a distinctive ribbing on the prodissoconch which differs both from most coastal *Nucula* spp. and most of the South African species. We believe this should be emphasized as an indication of a hitherto neglected but apparently useful character of some deep-water Atlantic nuculid species.

RESUMEN

Se encontraron tres especies en el talud continental frente a Namibia, de las cuales dos son nuevas para la ciencia: *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp. y *N. nama* n. sp. Se realizó una comparación con especies morfológicamente similares del Atlántico oriental y Sudáfrica de la familia Nuculidae. *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp. se encontró viva en sedimentos limosos con alto contenido orgánico en las profundidades batiales superiores frente a la región del Kunene en el noroeste de Namibia. *Nucula nama* n. sp. solo se conoce de un solo individuo vivo tomado en un entorno similar. Las dos nuevas especies tienen una escultura radial distintiva en la prodisoconcha que difiere tanto de la mayoría de las *Nucula* spp. costeras como de la mayoría de las especies sudafricanas. Se hipotetiza que este carácter hasta ahora descuidado pero aparentemente útil indica un parentesco con algunas especies de nuculidos del Atlántico de aguas profundas.

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KEY WORDS: Mollusca, SE Atlantic Ocean, western Africa.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, SE Océano Atlántico, África occidental.

* Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (IOW), Warnemünde, Germany, michael.zettler@io-warnemuende.de. Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5437-5495>

** Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven, Germany, leon.hoffman@senckenberg.de. Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0205-186X>

INTRODUCTION

Species of the family Nuculidae Gray, 1824 (Bivalvia: Protobranchia) live in all oceans of the world from the intertidal zone to abyssal plains, mostly in silty mud (HUBER, 2010). Presently, about 168 valid species are contained in 11 genera (MOLLUSCABASE 2021). The genus *Nucula* Lamarck, 1799 contains nearly half (83 taxa) of the valid species in the family.

Many papers discuss species in *Nucula* living in the eastern Atlantic Ocean. A global inventory of all genera in the family Nuculidae was recently given by HUBER (2010). COSEL & GOFAS (2019) provided an inventory of tropical shallow-water bivalves from western Africa including five species from Angola: *Nucula nucleus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *N. crassicostata* Smith, 1872, *N. mariae* Nolf, 2006, *N. nicklesi* Cosel, 1995 and *N. nitidosa* Winckworth, 1930. Unfortunately, information on Namibian species relevant for this study was not included in their work. ALLEN (2008) mentioned a single record of *Ennucula granulosa* (Verrill, 1884) off Namibia (depth 622 m); we did not encounter this species in our studies. Apart from abyssal finds of *Pronucula benguelana* A. H. Clarke, 1961 in the Cape Basin (CLARKE 1961, BARNARD 1963; RHIND & ALLEN 1992), several studies provide information on the occurrence of only *Nucula nucleus* in Namibia and SW Africa (THIELE & JAECKEL 1931; BARNARD 1964; BREMNER 1978; KILBURN 1999; STEFFANI & PULFRICH 2013; EDELMAN-FURSTENBERG 2014; COMPTON & BERGH 2016; BERGH & COMPTON 2020). Our studies confirmed three species from offshore Namibia: *Nucula nucleus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and two new congeneric species described herein.

SYSTEMATICS

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758
Family NUCULIDAE Gray, 1824
Genus *Nucula* Lamarck, 1799

This study is part of an ongoing inventory of Bivalvia from offshore Namibia. Other studies recently reported on Namibian bivalve species in *Neocardia* G.B. Sowerby III, 1892 (HOFFMAN & FREIWALD 2019), on Galeommatoida J.E. Gray, 1840, *Waisiuconcha* Beets, 1942 and *Nuculana* Link, 1807 (ZETTLER & HOFFMAN 2021a-c) and on *Polittitapes* Chiamenti, 1900 (ZETTLER & ALF 2021a).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Live specimens and empty shells were obtained from dredge hauls and sediment samples from the sea bottom during cruises to offshore Namibia. Sediment samples were sieved on board retaining the fractions greater than 1 mm. Initially the live-collected specimens were stored on formalin; the preservation fluid was later replaced by ethanol (96%). All mollusc material was hand-sorted under a low-magnification binocular and colour photographs were taken of selected samples at IOW using a camera mounted on a stereomicroscope. High-resolution imaging was done on selected samples using the scanning electron microscope at SaM (Vega3-Tescan; incident electron energy 10 KeV, high-vacuum imaging using secondary electrons). The SEM samples were coated with gold to facilitate imaging.

The holotypes and paratypes of the newly described species are retained in the Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt am Main (SMF). The remaining material is kept in the reference collection at the Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (IOW), Warnemünde, Germany.

Figures 1-6. *Nucula nucleus*, Namibia. 1-3; M157-11, 154 m, height 9 mm, length 10 mm, width 5 mm; 4: M157-36, 317 m, right valve, height 7 mm, length 8 mm; 5: M157-38, 187 m, right valve, height 8 mm, length 9 mm; 6: M157-36, 317 m, left valve, height 7 mm, length 8 mm.

Figuras 1-6. Nucula nucleus, Namibia. 1-3: M157-11, 154 m, altura 9 mm, longitud 10 mm, ancho 5 mm; 4: M157-36, 317 m, valva derecha, altura 7 mm, longitud 8 mm; 5: M157-38, 187 m, valva derecha, altura 8 mm, longitud 9 mm; 6: M157-36, 317 m, valva izquierda, altura 7 mm, longitud 8 mm.

Nucula nucleus (Linnaeus, 1758) (Figs. 1-6)

Material examined: NAMIBIA • 2 valves; 22.499°S, 13.533°E; 156 m; 18 Sept. 2011; MSM18-NAM-BE21; dredge. • 5 valves; 23.000°S, 13.499°E; 242 m; 25 Aug. 2019; M157-10; dredge. • 1 shell, 20 valves; 23.000°S, 13.683°E, 154 m; 26 Aug. 2019; M157-11; dredge. • 2 valves; 17,267°S, 11,501°E; 151 m, 1 Sept. 2019; M157-28; dredge. • 2 valves; 25.000°S, 13.733°E, 317 m; 6 Sept. 2019; M157-36; dredge. • 20 valves; 25.000°S, 13.917°E; 187 m, 7 Sept. 2019; M157-38; dredge. • 4 valves; 18.000°S, 11.717°E; 95 m, 23 Jan. 2022; MSM105-41; dredge. • 10 valves; 25.000°S, 13.917°E; 186 m, 29 Jan. 2022; MSM105-64; dredge. • 12 valves; 26.000°S, 14,897°E; 27 m; 1 Feb. 2022; MSM105-78; dredge.

Remarks: *Nucula nucleus* is the type species of the genus. The species is known from Norway southward to Senegal (Dakar); Côte d'Ivoire (only the Abidjan region); an isolated record of worn empty valves from northern Angola (Luanda) and into the Mediterranean Sea (HUBER 2010; COSEL & GOFAS 2019; ALF ET AL. 2020; ZETTLER & ALF 2021b). Additionally records are known from southern Angola (Baia dos Tigres) by THIELE & JAECKEL

(1931) and from Namibia (Lüderitz) by BARNARD (1964). A few dozen records are available from investigations of quaternary deposits along the Namibian shore (e.g. BREMNER 1978; COMPTON & BERGH 2016; BERGH & COMPTON 2020). Our study confirmed its distribution in offshore waters of Namibia. However, only subrecent single valves were observed. Shells were found in a water depth range between 27 and 320 m.

Nucula kunenensis n. sp. (Figs. 7-17)

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Type material. *Holotype*: NAMIBIA • 1 live-collected specimen (Fig. 7); off SW Kunene region; 20.652°S, 11.898°E; 866 m; 07 Sept. 2011; MSM18-NAM014; dredge; SMF358994. *Paratypes*: NAMIBIA • 1 live-collected specimen (Figs. 15-17); 20.556°S, 12.060°E; 550 m; 07 Sept. 2011; MSM18-NAM012; dredge; SMF358995 • 3 live-collected specimens (Figs. 8-14); 20.604°S, 11.979°E; 707 m; 07 Sept. 2011; MSM18-NAM013; dredge; SMF358996-358997 • 4 live-collected specimens; same data as for holotype; SMF358998.

Other material investigated: • 16 live collected specimens; 17.267°S, 11.150°E; 1101 m; 31 Aug. 2019; M157-26; box corer. • 9 live collected specimens; 25.000°S, 13.549°E; 627 m; 04 Sept. 2019; M157-34; multi-corer. • 2 live collected specimens; 18.000°S, 11.283°E; 1006 m; 22 Jan. 2022; MSM105-35; box corer. • 1 live collected specimen; 27.000°S, 13.900°E; 586 m; 3 Feb. 2022; MSM105-86; box corer. • 1 live collected specimen; 27.000°S, 14.267°E; 383 m; 3 Feb. 2022; MSM105-89; dredge.

Type locality: Namibia, off SW Kunene region, 20.652°S, 11.898°E, depth 866 m.

Etymology: The name refers to the type locality off the Kunene region.

Description: Small globose shell (height 4.1 mm, length 4.3 mm, width 2.3 mm), equivalve, subequilateral, umbo posteriorly, rounded triangular outline; white opaque shell, light greenish-yellow glossy periostracum, internally nacreous.

Prodissoconch: Flattened valves, nearly circular outline; sculpture with about 15 broad radial ridges; transition to dissoconch is clear by change in sculpture and raised prodissoconch; height 0.17 mm, length 0.17 mm; (Fig. 12 of paratype).

Dissoconch: Globose valves with rounded angular outline; rounded protruding umbo posterior to midline, tilted backwards; convex dorsal- and ventral margins, truncated antero-dorsally (Figs. 7-10, 13-14, 16-17). Sculpture with many regular inconspicuous radial ribs, irregular commarginal growth stages and numerous fine growth lines; few coarse growth stages near the margin. Lunula and escutcheon inconspicuous (Figs. 10, 17). Internally smooth and glossy with blunt edge (Figs. 11, 15); fine crenulations on ventral edge aligned with external radial sculpture. Anterior and posterior adductor muscle scars of equal height; posterior scar narrower. Pallial line without sinus, delimiting broad margin parallel to ventral edge. Short straight posterior hinge plate, 6-7 strong teeth with rectangular cross-section projecting vertically from hinge,

teeth near umbo very short. Longer convex anterior hinge plate, 11-12 teeth arranged similarly to anterior part of the hinge; with somewhat chevron-shaped cross-section in central teeth. Chondrophore anterior to umbo, pyriform in outline; situated in line with posterior hinge teeth and beneath the small, proximal anterior hinge teeth (Fig. 11).

Variability: Outline slightly angular anteriorly in some specimens; crenulations heavier in larger specimens. Length up to 4.5 mm; height up to 4.3 mm.

Differential diagnosis: We present a comparison with the type species *Nucula nucleus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and with the more similar eastern Atlantic *N. nitidosa* Winckworth, 1930, the central West African *N. crassicostata* E.A. Smith, 1872 and *N. nicklesi* Cosel, 1995 and the South African *N. subluxa* Kilburn, 1999 and *N. planiculmen* Kilburn, 1999.

Nucula nucleus is larger, heavier, strongly truncated posteriorly with the umbo placed more posteriorly from the midline (Figs. 1-6). *N. nucleus* is known in the Mediterranean Sea and the eastern Atlantic from Western Europe to South Africa.

The similar *Nucula nitidosa* can be differentiated by its more triangular antero-ventral and postero-ventral margins and in being less tumid. West African specimens may reach 8.5 mm in length (COSEL & GOFAS, 2019: 74, figs. 1.3-1.4). The species has been reported

Figures 7-17. *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp., Namibia. 7. Holotype, MSM18-NAM014, 866 m, height 4.1 mm, length 4.3 mm. 8-14. Paratypes, MSM18-NAM013, 707 m. 8: height 3.1 mm, length 3.4 mm; 9: height 2.5 mm, length 2.9 mm; 10-14: height 3.2 mm, length 3.6 mm, width 2.0 mm, prodissoconch height 0.17 mm, length 0.17 mm. 15-17. Paratype, MSM18-NAM012, 550 m, height 3.7 mm, length 4.1 mm, width 2.2 mm.

Figuras 7-17. *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp., Namibia. 7. Holotipo, MSM18-NAM014, 866 m, altura 4,1 mm, longitud 4,3 mm. 8-14. Paratipos, MSM18-NAM013, 707 m. 8: altura 3,1 mm, longitud 3,4 mm; 9: altura 2,5 mm, longitud 2,9 mm; 10-14: altura 3,2 mm, longitud 3,6 mm, ancho 2,0 mm, altura prodissoconcha 0,17 mm, longitud 0,17 mm. 15-17. Paratipo, MSM18-NAM012, 550 m, altura 3,7 mm, longitud 4,1 mm, ancho 2,2 mm.

off northern Angola (HUBER 2010; COSEL & GOFAS 2019) and it is also known from the NE Atlantic and into the Mediterranean Sea (HUBER 2010; ALF ET AL. 2020; ZETTLER & ALF 2021b). The tropical West African *Nucula crassicostata* is a smaller species with a similar outline but it is less tumid and it has strong commarginal growth ridges (COSEL &

GOFAS 2019). Another tropical West African species is *Nucula nicklesi*; it is less tumid and its umbo is placed more posteriorly (COSEL & GOFAS 2019).

The South African *Nucula subluxa* has a similar outline but shows many sharp growth ridges and its adult size is only 2.4 mm; its prodissoconch is larger (0.27 mm length) and has a pitted sculp-

ture (KILBURN, 1999: 252, figs. 7-10). The South African *Nucula planiculmen* has a more obliquely elongated outline with a similarly smooth outer surface and its maximum size is only 2.5 mm (KILBURN, 1999: 254, figs. 11-15); its prodissoconch is larger (0.37 mm length) with a pitted sculpture.

The ribbing on the prodissoconch appears to be important and may be used as a feature for a complex to which this species and the next belong. It was also seen on deep water specimens from off Cape St. Vincent and Morocco illustrated by SALAS (1996: 36, figs. 4-6) as *Nucula tumidula* Malm, 1860 (identification still to be checked as the type locality is in Norway). THIELE & JAECKEL (1931: 195) mentioned *N. tumidula* from off South Africa (Agulhas Bank), a record which KILBURN (1999) assigned to *N. nucleus*. However, he wrote that an unresolved sample from off Port St Johns, South Africa in 300-540 m (Natal Museum Pietermaritzburg C9698) does in fact closely resemble a series of *N. tumidula* from 300-500 m off Norway (Natal Museum Pietermaritzburg K2932: K. W. Ockelmann), although there is less resemblance to the figures in SALAS (1996: figs. 4-6). To be sure whether the *tumidula*-like species of South Africa correspond to *N. kunenen-*

sis, more comparative material is needed.

RHIND & ALLEN (1992: 65) mentioned abundant specimens of *Nucula atacellana* Schenck, 1939 in 2000-4600 m depth in the Angola Basin. Possibly this deep water species belongs to these *tumidula*-like nukulids with a ribbed prodissoconch and can also be discussed despite that the record from Rhind & Allen is much deeper than the scope of this manuscript. Unfortunately the images given by RHIND & ALLEN (1992) and SCHENCK (1939) show no view of the prodissoconch. However, no ribbing can be seen in the very good illustration given by SALAS (1996: figs. 7-9), so that major doubts remain. Overall, *N. atacellana* also has much more definite commarginal ridges and radial striations so that the shell surface appears reticulated.

Remarks: Fresh material of *Nucula kunenensis* n. sp. shows corrosion on the prodissoconchs and frequently on the external dissoconch; an intact prodissoconch could not yet be figured. Anatomic and molecular details are unknown; soft parts have not been studied.

The latitudinal distribution range is 17°S-27°S; the bathymetric range is 383-1101 m.

Nucula nama n. sp. (Figs. 18-23)

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Type material. *Holotype:* NAMIBIA • 1 live collected specimen (Figs. 18-22); off SW Kunene region; 20.652°S, 11.898°E; 866 m.; 7 Sept. 2011; MSM18-NAM014; dredge, SMF358999.

Type locality: Namibia, off SW Kunene region, 20.652°S, 11.898°E, depth 866 m.

Etymology: The species is named after the ethnic group and its associated language in Namibia: Nama.

Description: Small globose shell (height 2.2 mm, length 2.7 mm, width 1.1 mm), equivalve, subequilateral with umbo slightly posterior to midline, angular outline; white opaque shell, brown glossy periostracum, internally nacreous, (Figs. 18-23).

Prodissoconch: Flattened valves, oblong outline, truncated at dorsal

margin; sculpture with few broad radial ridges; transition to dissoconch is clear by change in sculpture; height 0.14 mm, length 0.19 mm (Fig. 20, 23).

Dissoconch: Slightly globose valves with transversely oblong outline; convex dorsal- and ventral margins, truncated anterior- and posterior margins. Umbo placed posterior to

Figures 18-23. *Nucula nama* n. sp. , holotype, Namibia; MSM18-NAM014, 866 m, height 2.2 mm, length 2.7 mm, width 1.1 mm, prodissoconch height 0.14 mm, length 0.19 mm.

Figuras 18-23. *Nucula nama* n. sp. , holotipo, Namibia; MSM18-NAM014, 866 m, altura 2,2 mm, longitud 2,7 mm, ancho 1,1 mm, altura prodissoconcha 0,14 mm, longitud 0,19 mm.

midline inclined posteriorly. Sculpture with many regular inconspicuous radial riblets and irregular commarginal growth stages and numerous fine growth lines (Fig. 18). Lunula and escutcheon absent. Internally smooth and glossy with blunt edge; fine crenulations on ventral margin aligned with external radial sculpture (Figs. 21, 22). Anterior and posterior adductor muscle scars of equal height; posterior scar narrower. Pallial line without sinus, delimiting a broad margin parallel to ventral edge. Short straight posterior hinge plate, 5 teeth of moderate size with rectangular cross-section projecting vertically from hinge, teeth near umbo very short. Longer convex anterior hinge plate, 8 teeth arranged similarly to anterior hinge plate. Chondrophore anterior to umbo, pyriform in outline, placed at dorsal margin in line with anterior and posterior teeth.

Differential diagnosis: We present a comparison with the sympatric *Nucula*

nucleus and with the more similar eastern Atlantic *N. nitidosa*, the central West African *N. crassicostata* and *N. nicklesi*, the South African *N. subluxa* and *N. planiculmen* and the sympatric *N. kunenensis* n. sp.

A rectangular outline is known for juvenile specimens of some species in the eastern Atlantic (like *Nucula nucleus*) but their juvenile shells are less tumid and their prodissoconchs are larger.

The sympatric *Nucula nucleus* has a much larger adult size of 10 mm and a prodissoconch length of approximately 0.3 mm (COSEL & GOFAS 2019). *N. nitidosa* has a larger adult shell size and a similar prodissoconch but it has a triangular outline and its valves are less tumid (COSEL & GOFAS 2019). The West African *N. crassicostata* is less tumid and it has a more oblique outline and commarginal costae on the dissoconch (COSEL & GOFAS 2019). The West African *N. nicklesi* is less tumid with a more oblique outline (COSEL & GOFAS 2019). The South African *Nucula*

subluxa is similar in size but shows many sharp growth ridges and its prodissoconch is larger (0.27 mm length) with a pitted sculpture (KILBURN, 1999). The South African *Nucula planiculmen* has a similar size and sculpture but it has a more obliquely elongated outline and its prodissoconch is much larger (0.37 mm length) with a pitted sculpture (KILBURN, 1999).

Nucula kunenensis n. sp. is more tumid and has a more rounded outline, its periostracum has a greenish yellow colour; *N. nama* n. sp. has slightly flattened valves, an angular outline and a brown periostracum.

DISCUSSION

Three species of *Nucula* were found in bottom samples from Namibia in this study: *Nucula nucleus*, *N. kunenensis* n. sp. and *N. nama* n. sp. Angola to the North (5 species: HUBER 2010; COSEL & GOFAS 2019) and South Africa (9 species: KILBURN 1999) show a larger diversity in Nuculidae. It is possible that more species will be found with increased sampling across the large area offshore Namibia.

Both new species were found in muddy sediment with high organic content in the upper bathyal zone off Namibia. *N. kunenensis* occurred in a depth range between 550 and 1101 m and *N. nama* at 866 m. In contrast to the shelf, this depth zone is hardly influenced by the oxygen minimum zone. The oxygen values were between 1 and 3 ml/l.

ALLEN (2008) mentioned *Ennucula granulosa* (Verrill, 1884) off Namibia (23°S, depth 622 m). This is a species with a smooth ventral margin with its type locality in the Caribbean Sea, also occurring in the deeper basins of North America and Western Europe (HUBER 2010). An occurrence off Namibia is unlikely, but not impossible. However, no smooth-margined nuculids were encountered in our material so far.

The two new species have a distinctive ribbing on the prodissoconch which

Remarks: Nucula nama n. sp. is only known from the holotype. Variability, anatomical and molecular details are unknown. The small size and relatively few teeth possibly suggest a subadult specimen. However, the sympatric *N. kunenensis* n. sp. has similar sizes for the prodissoconch and dissoconch. Moreover, several South African species like for example *N. subluxa* and *N. planiculmen* also show relatively few teeth and a similar small size. For the discussion of the *tumidula*-like nuculids with a ribbed prodissoconch see the remarks to *N. kunenensis* n. sp.

differs both from most coastal *Nucula* spp. (see SEM pictures in SALAS, 1996 and GOFAS & SALAS, 1996) and from the Cape species described by Kilburn (1999). Interestingly, both species described by KILBURN (1999) from the Cape Province are small but have a relatively large prodissoconch with a pitted sculpture. Hence, we assume that the origins of the new species are Atlantic and that Kilburn's species originate from a different region, like for example the Indian Ocean.

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